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Depositional mode and Provenance of Kopili sandstones from parts of Dima Hasao District, Assam, NE India: Evidence from Grain size distribution and Heavy mineral assemblage

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Abstract

This study presents a record of the depositional mode and provenance of the Kopili sandstones outcropped in and around Umrangso, the Dima Hasao district of Assam, India using proxies such as grain size and heavy mineral study. The Grain size study reveals that the sandstones of the Kopili formation consist predominantly of fine-grained sands mixed with medium sands. The grain size statistical parameters divulge that the sandstones are characterized mostly by moderately sorted sands, coarse skewed to near symmetrical, leptokurtic to extremely leptokurtic nature. The frequency distribution curves reflect mostly bimodal as well as polymodal distribution of sediments. The Linear Discriminant Function analysis indicates shallow marine beach sub environment in agitated water depositional condition for the Kopili sediments. The CM pattern discloses that saltation and suspension are the dominant transporting modes.

The Heavy mineral analysis discerns that opaques dominate over transparent heavies. Transparent heavies in decreasing order of abundance are zircon, tourmaline, rutile, clinopyroxene, staurolite, hornblende, garnet, chlorite and epidote. The zircon-tourmaline-rutile (ZTR) maturity index (average 53.15%) discloses sub-mature to mature nature of the Kopili sandstones. The heavy mineral assemblage corroborates their mixed provenance (silicic igneous and metamorphic) for the Kopili sandstones.

Keywords: Provenance, Statistical parameters, Kopili formation, Dima Hasao District.

Introduction

The study of clastic sediments from the standpoint of grain size distribution in conjunction with heavy mineral analysis provides the basis for understanding depositional conditions and the provenance of sediments. A sediment population of variable particle size incorporating various heavy mineral concentrates describes sediments from the source to sink. The grain size analyses often describe clastic sediments to understand hydrodynamic condition, paleoenvironmental features, provenance, transit mechanisms and sedimentary environment classification^{1,4,6,9,27}. The grain size statistical

parameters are utilized to distinguish beach, dune and river sediments and to reveal the mode of transport and energy conditions, sorting and depositional conditions before final induration^{3,10,12}.

Heavy minerals are sensitive indicators of provenance. So examining them helps in the identification of petrographic provinces, tectonic settings, source regions as well as their mineralogical makeup^{5,13,14,16,17}. The Late Eocene Kopili formation⁷ is very well exposed in the Dima Hasao District of Assam (Previously known as North Cachar Hills); however, the type section outcrops along the Kopili river²³. So far, very few investigations^{24,25,30} such as early tertiary stratigraphical study and palynological investigation were employed in some pockets of North Cachar Hills, Assam. Owing to inadequate available data, the authors attempted to investigate the area to better understand the provenance, mode of deposition and environment of deposition of Kopili sediments.

Geological setup of the study area

The Kopili formation, the youngest lithostratigraphic unit of the Jaintia Group outcrops on the southern and southeastern parts of Shillong Plateau (Khasi and Jaintia Hills) in Meghalaya and in the Dima Hasao District of Assam. The present study was employed in and around Umrangso town, the Dima Hasao District (Figure 1). The Kopili formation comprises calcareous grey shales intercalated with sandstone, siltstone, argillaceous limestone and strings of coal. The Kopili formation developed in the study area is conformable and sandwiched between the overlying Barail sediments and the underlying Garampani limestone formation^{24,25}.

Its base is irregular and uneven with grey to dark grey splintery shale, flaky to needle-like non-sticky fissile shale, fossiliferous marl beds, calcareous sandstone, argillaceous limestone and mudstone litho units interbedded with calcareous sandstone and argillaceous limestone. The lithology at the top of the Garampani limestone formation is calcareous compact shale interbedded with thick sandstone beds, limestone and thin marl units. An arenaceous unit dominates the upper portion of the Kopili formation.

Below this unit, are splintery grey shale units of various types including compact grey shale, fissile, flaky dark grey shale, splintery clayey shale with sticky clay shale and sporadic sandstone units. Table 1 and figure 2 represent the

generalized stratigraphic succession and elevation map of the study area respectively.

Material and Methods

Samples analyzed in the present study were collected systematically from the sections exposed in and around the

Umrangso town, Sampling was conducted parallel to the beddings to avoid mixing of populations. A total of 20 representative sandstone samples were analyzed for the present study. Of this total, 10 samples were studied for grain size distribution and 10 for heavy mineral analysis.

Figure 1: Location map of the study area showing sample points, traverses and the Kopili River

For the grain size study, about 100g samples were disaggregated using a porcelain mortar pestle and air dried followed by coning and quartering method. Sieving was performed following the standard method⁸ at half phi (ϕ) intervals for about 15 minutes and fractions retained on each sieve were weighed separately. The weighted fractions were converted into cumulative weight percentages. The statistical parameters: median (M_d), mean (M_z), standard deviation (σ_1), skewness (Sk_i) and kurtosis (K_G) were calculated using the standard formulae⁹ (Table 2), tabulated (Table 3) and their frequency distribution curves were made (Figure 3a and figure 3b).

The M_d indicates the midpoint of the grain size distribution. The M_z denotes the central tendency or the average size of the sediments. The σ_1 is a measure of sorting of sediments as well as the velocity conditions of the depositing agents. The Sk_i is a metric of asymmetry of frequency distributions. The K_G is used to determine the peakedness of a frequency curve. The frequency distribution curves represent the predominance of particular size classes of grain size distribution. The linear Discriminant Function (LDF) analysis was conducted to characterize sediments in terms of their depositional environments. The four discriminant functions (Y1, Y2, Y3 and Y4) were estimated following the standard formula²² (Table 4 and table 5) and plotted (Figure 4). The CM pattern¹⁸ of sediments was created by plotting C (the one percentile) against M (the median diameter) for each sample (Figure 5). It is a measure of describing agents of deposition and it represents sediment of an environment. The energy of the transporting medium as well as the nature and kind of the sediments are all factors in the connection between C and M³¹. For heavy mineral separation, 10g of fine sand fraction, passed through 80 mesh-size sieve were taken by following the conventional technique¹⁵, using Bromoform (sp. gr.2.89).

Heavy minerals were washed, dried and mounted with Canada balsam on glass slides. Heavy minerals were detected (Figure 6) based on their optical characteristics and their percentage concentrations were calculated (Table 6). The metrics such as the ZTR (zircon-tourmaline-rutile) index, the length-breadth and the elongation ratios (L/B) of zircons were determined. The ZTR index measures the mineralogical maturity of sediments by calculating the proportion of zircon, tourmaline and rutile among the transparent heavy minerals¹⁴.

The ZTR triangular diagram (Figure 7) is divided into three primary tiers: A, B and C, each of which is divided into two blocks: A1 and A2, B1 and B2 and C1 and C2. The recalculated values of zircon, tourmaline and rutile are displayed on the ZTR triangle diagram. The lengths and breadths of the zircons were calculated using a mechanical stage attached to the petrographic microscope. The frequency percentages of zircon's length-breadth data were estimated and plotted (Figure 8a and figure 8b). The elongation ratio (L/B) of each zircon was determined,

converted into frequency percentage and plotted (Figure 9). Further, Smithson's scatter diagrams²⁶ were made by plotting the length values of the zircons on the Y axis and the breadth values on the X axis (Figure 10).

Results and Discussion

Grain size statistics and depositional mode: Statistical parameters of grain size distribution act as an effective tool in characterizing sedimentary environments. The most commonly used statistical parameters such as mean size (M_z), median (M_d), standard deviation (σ_1), skewness (Sk_i) and kurtosis (K_G) were evaluated using the conventional formulae⁹ (Table 2 and table 3). The M_z of the studied samples ranges from 1.10 to 2.87 ϕ , average 2.41 ϕ which indicates predominance of fine sand. The majority of the samples has M_z over 2 ϕ except for one sample ($M_z=1.1\phi$). This slight shift in M_z is due to instabilities in the energy condition at the time of deposition. The fine-grained nature of the samples indicates a somewhat low-energy state of deposition.

The minor occurrence of medium sand fraction in the samples may be due to limited input and abrupt increase in the energy conditions¹¹. The σ_1 values vary from 0.60 to 1.50, average 0.94 which reflects moderately well-sorted (MWS) to poorly-sorted (PS) sediments. For 60% of the samples, the σ_1 is less than 1 while the σ_1 of the remaining 40% is between 1.01 and 1.50. The moderately sorted (MS) sands appear in 40% of the samples ($\sigma_1=0.74-0.91$) whereas the MWS sands appear in 20 % of the samples ($\sigma_1=0.60-0.65$). The remaining 40% of the samples are occupied by PS sands ($\sigma_1=1.01$ to 1.50). The predominance of MWS could be due to the depositing agents' repeated back-and-forth movement or winnowing action, as well as subsequent incursion of already sorted sediments into the depositional environment^{2,21}.

The Sk_i values ranging from -0.60 to 0.04 (average -0.25) reflect the near-symmetrical (NS) to very coarse skewed (VCS) nature of the samples. About 80% of the samples are negatively skewed ($Sk_i=-0.60$ to -0.2). The remaining 20 % are positively skewed ($Sk_i=0.02$ to 0.04). The majority of the samples are coarse skewed (CS) to very coarse skewed (VCS); while very few samples are NS. In general, the presence of NS and finely skewed sediments implies the onset of deposition of fine material and the removal of coarser material. The presence of fine skewed sediments suggests much winnowing or prolonged transit. The NS distribution of sediments suggests moderate energy conditions in the depositional environment.

The K_G values ranging from 1.02 to 3.21 with an average of 1.6 typifies that 60% of the samples are leptokurtic, 20% are very leptokurtic, 10 % extremely leptokurtic and 10% are mesokurtic. The leptokurtic character of the samples suggests fluctuating energy conditions during deposition²⁸. The variations in kurtosis values are on account of variations in the flow characteristics of the transportation and

depositional medium. The mesokurtic to leptokurtic nature of the samples points to the constant addition of finer fractions after the winnowing action of the depositing agent and preservation of their initial characters during deposition. The frequency distribution curves (Figure 3a) of the present study are characterized by bimodal nature followed by polymodal and unimodal nature for most of the samples. The bimodal curves have prominent peaks between 1.5 and 4Ø. The polymodal curves reflect dominant peaks between 1.5 to 4 Ø. The frequency distribution curves corroborating the dominance of bimodal distribution of sediments are ascribed to derivation from a mixed provenance. The unimodal curves show prominent peaks at 3Ø and the unimodal nature of these curves suggests a consistent or steady depositional process during the deposition of sediments.

In addition, the occurrence of dominant peaks between 2.5 to 4Ø, as well as the unimodality characteristics perhaps reveals a low-energy condition of deposition. The cumulative curves of the studied samples are shown in figure 3b. The slopes of the middle portion of the cumulative curves have bearing on the sorting of sediments. The cumulative frequency curves show that most of the samples are characterized by steep slopes, which suggest good sorting of sediments. The steep slopes have concave middle down portions at 3Ø and become gentle toward the finer ends. The rest of the cumulative curves display broad and gentle slopes and hence imply poor sorting resulting from low kinetic energy and velocity. The fairly wide and gentle

sloping nature of the cumulative curves indicates relatively low kinetic energy and velocity regime of the depositing media.

The Linear Discriminant Function (LDF) analysis (Figure 4) reveals that the Y1, Y2, Y3 and Y4 values vary from -3.03224 to 7.7257, 87.0059 to 182.9009, -19.1464 to -1.9511 and 4.5210 to 15.2534 respectively. The Y1 values show that 90% of the samples are from the beach sub environment; the remaining 10% from the aeolian environment. With regard to the Y2 values, all of the samples fall in the shallow marine environment. From Y3 values, it is apparent that 80% of the samples fall in the shallow marine environment and the remaining 20% fall in the fluvial (deltaic) environment. Y4 values reflect that 70% samples are from the turbidity current deposit with 30% from the fluvial (deltaic) deposit. Also, the bivariate plot of Y2 against Y1 (Figure 4a) shows that about 80% of the samples fall in the shallow marine beach environment, in agitated water.

The remaining samples lie in the aeolian shallow agitated water environment. Plot of Y2 against Y3 (Figure 4b) shows that all of the samples fall in the shallow marine agitated environment. The binary plot of Y4 against Y3 (Figure 4c) indicates that the majority of the samples fall in the turbidity current shallow marine field and the remaining in the fluvial turbidity current field. Overall, the LDF analysis suggests that the deposition of Kopili sediments took place under the shallow marine beach sub environment in agitated water.

Table 2
Formulae for graphical calculation of grain size parameters⁹

1. Graphic mean (M_z) = $\frac{\phi_{16} + \phi_{50} + \phi_{84}}{3}$
2. Graphic standard deviation (σ_1) = $\frac{\phi_{84} - \phi_{16}}{4} + \frac{\phi_{95} - \phi_5}{6.6}$
3. Graphic skewness (Sk_i) = $\frac{\phi_{16} + \phi_{84} - 2\phi_{50}}{2(\phi_{84} - \phi_{16})} + \frac{\phi_5 + \phi_{95} - 2\phi_{50}}{2(\phi_{95} - \phi_5)}$
4. Graphic kurtosis (K_G) = $\frac{\phi_{95} - \phi_5}{2.44(\phi_{75} - \phi_{25})}$

Table 3
Grain size statistical parameters of Kopili sandstones from the study area

Sample No.	(M_d)	(M_z)	Standard deviation (σ_1)		Skewness (Sk_i)		Kurtosis (K_G)	
KP1	2.91	2.84	0.82	MS	-0.39	VCS	1.21	Leptokurtic
KP2	2.51	2.47	0.60	MWS	0.02	NS	1.83	Very leptokurtic
KP3	2.4	2.30	0.65	MWS	-0.16	CS	1.41	Leptokurtic
KP4	3.1	2.87	1.20	PS	-0.35	VCS	1.44	Leptokurtic
KP5	2.31	2.48	0.90	MS	0.04	NS	1.46	Leptokurtic
KP6	3.15	2.80	1.01	PS	-0.59	VCS	1.30	Leptokurtic
KP7	3	2.63	1.02	PS	-0.60	VCS	1.35	Leptokurtic
KP8	2.2	2.07	0.74	MS	-0.44	VCS	3.21	Extremely Leptokurtic
KP9	1.2	1.08	1.50	PS	-0.04	NS	1.02	Mesokurtic
KP10	2.5	2.58	0.91	MS	-0.02	CS	1.74	Very Leptokurtic

Figure 3: (a) Grain size frequency distribution curves and (b) Cumulative frequency distribution curves

The CM pattern (Figure 5) shows that the maximum sample points cluster mainly in the class II of segment OP which represent a mixture of rolling and suspension sediments. The remaining samples concentrate in the segment PQ of class V and segment NO of class I. The sample points falling in the segment NO indicate presence of rolling sediments in the samples. The sample points in both the segment OP and NO have values $C > 1000$ micron, values $100 < M < 200$ micron for the segment PO and values $200 < M$ micron for the segment NO. Samples falling in the segment PQ represent mixtures of suspension sediments and rolled grains ($C < 1000$ micron and $100 < M < 200$ micron).

The CM pattern of sample points reveals that the majority of the samples falls in the segment OP (class II); hence it

constitutes mixtures of rolled grains mixed with suspension sediments in variable proportion¹⁹.

Samples that fall in the segments NO (class I) and PQ (class V) indicate the presence of rolled grains and suspension sediments with rolling subpopulation in the samples respectively.

Heavy mineral analysis and provenance:

Morphological descriptions and statistical study: The heavy mineral assemblage of the Kopili formation comprises both transparent heavy minerals (Figure 6) such as zircon (Zr), tourmaline (Tr), rutile (Ru), garnet (Gr), chlorite (Ch), clinopyroxene (Cpx), staurolite (St), hornblende (Hb) and epidote (Ep) and opaques.

Figure 4: Linear discriminant function plots of Kopili sandstones. Plot A: Y1 vs Y2 distinguishes between Aeolian and beach environment; plot B: Y2 vs Y3 distinguishes between beach and shallow-marine sub-environment; plot C: Y3 vs Y4 distinguishes between marine turbidity and fluvial (deltaic) environment

Table 4
Linear discriminant function analysis formulae²²

$Y1 = -3.5688M_Z + 3.7016\sigma_1^2 - 2.0766Sk_i + 3.1135K_G$
$Y2 = 15.6534M_Z + 65.7091\sigma_1^2 + 18.1071Sk_i + 18.5043K_G$
$Y3 = 0.2852M_Z - 8.7604\sigma_1^2 - 4.8932Sk_i + 0.0482K_G$
$Y4 = 0.7215M_Z - 0.4030\sigma_1^2 + 6.7322Sk_i + 5.2927K_G$

Table 5
Linear discriminant function values of Kopili sandstones for environment interpretation
(Env.-Environment, A- aolian, B- beach, SM- shallow marine, F- fluvial and T- turbidity current)

Sample No.	Y1	Env.	Y2	Env.	Y3	Env.	Y4	Env.
KP1	-3.03224	A	104.2141	SM	-3.1546	SM	5.5104	T
KP2	-1.7982	B	96.9930	SM	-2.5409	SM	11.4806	F
KP3	-1.9327	B	87.0059	SM	-2.1936	SM	7.8770	T
KP4	0.2558	B	159.1413	SM	-9.9193	F	6.7845	T
KP5	-1.3629	B	119.7968	SM	-6.5149	SM	9.4778	T
KP6	-0.9139	B	124.9626	SM	-5.2761	SM	4.5210	T
KP7	-0.0558	B	124.1715	SM	-5.4144	SM	4.5592	T
KP8	5.5918	B	120.1604	SM	-1.9511	SM	15.2534	F
KP9	7.7257	B	182.9009	SM	-19.1464	F	4.9870	T
KP10	-0.6898	B	126.5613	SM	-6.3108	SM	10.5860	F

Figure 5: CM pattern of Kopili Sandstones indicating different modes of deposition¹⁹

Table 6

Percentage of transparent heavy minerals of Kopili sandstones. (Zr-zircon, Tr-tourmaline, Ru-rutile, Gr- garnet, Ch-chlorite, Cpx- clinopyroxene, St- staurolite, Hb- hornblende, Ep- epidote, ZTR- zircon-tourmaline- rutile)

Sample No.	Zr %	Tr %	Ru %	Gr %	Ch %	Cpx %	St %	Hb %	Ep %	ZTR%
HM1	29.97	7.16	3.18	0.26	0.26	-	0.32	-	-	86.86
HM2	4	0.8	0.8	2.93	-	2.93	-	0.53	-	33.33
HM3	6.49	3.85	0.48	0.24	0.48	-	0.21	-	-	69.23
HM4	2.84	1.77	0.35	0.35	-	-	0.13	-	-	65
HM5	3.70	1.39	1.39	-	0.46	1.86	-	-	-	56
HM6	7.14	0.71	1.43	-	-	2.86	0.51	0.71	-	41.93
HM7	2.7	0.39	1.56	0.78	-	2.7	0.54	-	1.17	26.09
HM8	4.08	2.04	1.02	-	-	12.24	-	4.08	-	18.92
HM9	23.65	9.97	2.56	0.28	-	1.99	0.27	0.57	-	84.10
HM10	5.71	0.52	0.26	-	0.26	0.52	0.72	-	-	50

Detrital Zircon accounts for 2.84 to 29.97%, averaging 9.03% of the total transparent heavy minerals. Zircons exhibit extreme relief, distinct black haloes and frequent carbonaceous impurities. Morphology varies from euhedral crystals through prismatic, pyramidal, moderately angular, rounded to well rounded and elongated. Colours vary from colourless to pink, orange, yellow and grey. Orange and pink varieties display colour zoning with surface indentations. Pyramidal and prismatic grains exhibit surface

pitting and frosting. Weak pleochroism, strong birefringence, surface pitting and frosting, together with lack of strong colours are conspicuous. Tourmaline crystals making up 0.39 to 9.97% with an average of 2.86% of the total heavies appear as angular, rounded to well rounded grains with moderate relief and colour zoning. Mineral inclusions are common and cleavages are rare. Presence of well rounded tourmaline crystals are found ubiquitous.

Figure 6: Micrographs of heavy mineral assemblage of Kopili sandstones taken under XPL. A1-B2 (zircon): euhedral, prismatic, subrounded to rounded with inclusions, surface pitting and colour zoning (A7, A8, B1 and B2). A7 and B2 show oscillatory zoning. B3-B6 (colored tourmaline): angular through sub rounded to well rounded. B7, B8, C1 and C2 (rutile): deep blood red to brownish red, bipyramidal and angular to sub rounded. C3, C4, C5, C6, C7 and C8: staurolite, hornblende, epidote, clinopyroxene, chlorite and garnet respectively

Figure 7: ZTR triangular plot for Kopili sandstones

The crystals display various shades of colours such as brown, green, orange and deep blue with moderate relief. Rutilites constitute 0.26 to 3.18%, with an average of 1.30% of the total heavies. They appear as prismatic, pyramidal, angular and sub rounded crystals surrounded by a thick black halo and show considerable degree of angularity. Colour varies from deep blood red to brownish red with striations and twinning. Staurolites falling in the range from 0.13 to 0.72 (average 0.27) occur as sub rounded crystals, display golden yellow colour and parallel extinction. Carbonaceous impurities are common. Hornblende crystals ranging from 0.53 to 4.08% (average 0.59) are predominantly prismatic with well-developed cleavages. Crystals show inclined extinction of about 23°. Ends of the crystals show some degree of rounding with some dissolution effect. Epidotes (1.17 %) appear as irregular crystals with high relief in the heavy mineral assemblage.

In some grains rounding of corners is seen. Parallel extinction and patchy arrangement of interference colours are the observed diagnostic features. The range of clinopyroxene grains varies from 0.52 to 12.24% with an average of 2.51% of the total heavies. The grains are characterized by pale green colour, prismatic habit with ragged terminations, well developed cleavages and higher extinction angle. Observed chlorite (0.26 to 0.48%) crystals are green, dominantly thin and flaky and irregularly shaped. They occupy a minor proportion among the total heavies. Garnets falling in the range between 0.24 and 2.93% with an average of 0.48% occur as sub rounded to well-rounded grains and exhibit high relief and isotropic character. Colour varies from colourless (in plane polarized light) to dark brown (in crossed polars).

The concentration of opaque is conspicuous among the non-transparent heavies. Opaques dominate over the transparent heavies in all the samples. The heavy minerals analysis reflecting varietal morphology and textural features indicates mixed provenance for the Kopili sediments. Presence of rounded zircons, rutilites and rounded tourmalines suggests their source from reworked sediments with considerable distance of transport. Small zircon crystals with more rounded varieties and prismatic habits discern their probable source from granitic rocks²⁰.

Other transparent heavies observed in trace amounts, such as chlorite, epidote and small pale brown tourmaline euhedra imply a low-rank metamorphic source. The presence of hornblende, clinopyroxene (diopside) and the blue-green variety of epidote suggests a high rank metamorphic source. Also, the presence of small detrital zircon euhedra reflects derivation of sediments from a silicic igneous source.

The statistical study reveals that zircon, tourmaline and rutile constitute 2.7-29.97 % (average 9.03 %), 0.39-9.97 % (average 2.86 %) and 0.26-3.18 % (average 1.3%) of the heavy mineral assemblage respectively (Table 6). Other heavy minerals include garnet (0.24 to 2.93 %, average

0.48%), chlorite (0.26 to 0.48%, average 0.15%), clinopyroxene (0.52 to 12.24 %, average average 2.51%), staurolite (0.13 to 0.72 %, average 0.27%), hornblende (0.53 to 4.08%, average 0.59% and epidote (1.17%).

The ZTR maturity index in this study ranges from 18.92 to 86.86% with an average of 53.15% (Table 6). This indicates that the Kopili sediments are sub-mature to mature. The ZTR triangular diagram (Figure 7) shows that the entire points cluster in the sub blocks A1 and A2 of the tier A. This indicates that zircons dominate over tourmaline and rutile in the studied samples.

The length – breadth data of zircons reveals that the zircons have somewhat larger length values (0.01 to 0.18) than their breadth values in the overall samples. Zircons with equal length and breadth values are also common. The lengths of zircons range from 0.06 to 0.04mm while the breadths range from 0.04 to 0.34mm.

The frequency distribution curves (Figure 8a and figure 8b) of zircons show dominant single peaked maxima for the majority of the samples. Some curves have broad peaks and multiple peaks. Some curves reflect a certain degree of asymmetry. The length-breadth frequency curves of zircons showing peaks toward the right suggest coarse nature and the peaks toward the left suggest fine nature²⁹. The elongation ratio (L/B) frequency curves (Figure 9) of zircons reflect prominent single peaked maxima for the majority of the samples.

Some curves are asymmetric in nature. The Zircon crystals have an overall elongation ratio of 1 to 4. The majority of them (83.33%) are slightly elongated (L/B = 1-2) and the rest are moderately elongated (16.67%, L/B=2-4)²⁰. The length-breadth measurements divulge that the zircons have slightly larger length values than their breadth in overall samples. As per elongation ratio statistics, slightly elongated zircons are more common, with length slightly greater than breadth. Frequency curves suggest both unimodal and bimodal nature of the sediments which are ascribed to a mixed provenance.

Smithson's diagrams (Figure 10) show that the catenae of points appear to rest flat on the 1:1 line and stretch somewhat toward the line 1:2. This implies that the detritus is derived from a metamorphic source²⁹. However, in certain samples, just a few points extend the catenae up to the 1:5 line.

This indicates that the sediments are in close proximity to their provenance and hence have suffered minimum wear and tear. The largest concentration of points is observed on the line 1:1. Towards the origin of coordinates, there are no sample points and the sample points disperse away from it. It signifies that the sediments suffer less attrition. Smithson's diagrams suggest presence of water laid sediments in the Kopili sandstones with addition of detritus from a new source or two distinct sources.

(a)

(b)
 Figure 8: (a) Length frequency curves of zircon for Kopili sandstones. Plot A to F shows unimodal distribution, G and H bimodal distribution and I and J asymmetric distribution of zircon in the samples, (b) Breadth frequency curves of zircon for Kopili sandstones

Figure 9: Elongation ratio curves of zircon for Kopili sandstones

Figure 10: Smithsonian diagrams of zircon for Kopili sandstones

Conclusion

The grain size study reveals that the Kopili sandstones are predominantly fine-grained, moderately well-sorted, leptokurtic and near symmetrical and deposited in a moderately low energy condition. The frequency distribution curves disclose mixing of two different modes in the grain size distribution. The LDF analysis divulges a shallow marine beach sub environment with agitated water condition for the deposition of Kopili sandstones.

The CM pattern indicates saltation and suspension as the chief modes of transport. The heavy mineral analysis discerns unimodal and bimodal character and a mixed provenance (metamorphic and silicic igneous) for the Kopili sediments. The ZTR maturity index discloses sub-mature to mature nature of the Kopili sandstones. The Smithsonian's diagrams reveal presence of water laid sediments in the Kopili sandstones with detritus from a new source or two different kinds of sources.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere gratitude to the Head, Department of Applied Geology, Dibrugarh University, Assam for providing laboratory facilities to carry out this work. The work of this study was financially supported by the Dibrugarh University Research Fellowship (DU/JR-A/DU Research Fellowship, Extension/2020/096), Dibrugarh University. The authors are grateful to Mr. Abhijit Kalita, (DGM, (E/M) NEEPCO, Umrangso, Assam) and Mr. Prem K. Chetri (MIS executive, Dalmia, Umrangso, Assam) for extending necessary help during the field survey. The

corresponding author thanks Mr. Ravi Shankar Kumar (Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Petroleum Technology, Amethi, India) for helping in preparation of the manuscript.

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(Received 18th September 2021, accepted 20th October 2021)